

High resolution results: Young Stellar Objects

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Astrophysical Jets

Young Stellar Objects (YSOs):

$$M \sim 1 M_{\odot}$$
$$l \sim 0.01 - 1 \text{ pc}, v_j \sim 100 - 400 \text{ km s}^{-1}$$
$$M_j \sim 10^{-6} - 10^{-8} M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$$
$$B \sim ?$$

Jets from Young Stars · HH1/HH2

HST · WFPC2

PRC95-24c · ST ScI OPO · June 6, 1995 · J. Hester (AZ State U.), NASA

Active Galactic Nuclei (AGN):

$$M \sim 10^8 - 10^9 M_{\odot}$$
$$l \sim 0.01 - 1 \text{ Mpc}, v_j \sim c$$
$$B \sim 10 - 100 \text{ mG}$$

Other properties?

Cygnus A (X-ray: NASA/CXC/SAO; Optical: NASA/STScI; Radio: NSF/NRAO/AUI/VLA)

Low mass star formation

Radio emission from YSOs: free-free

- $\lambda > 1 \text{ cm}$ ($\nu < 30 \text{ GHz}$)
- Class 0-II YSO jets
- Flux density $\sim 1 \text{ mJy}$
- Traces outflow

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 - $\alpha = 0.6$ “standard” spherical stellar wind (e.g. Panagia & Felli 1975)
 - $\alpha = 0.25$ “standard” collimated jet (Reynolds 1986)

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Motivation for metre wavelengths

- New territory!
- Detect optically thick surface (free-free)

$$\left(\frac{S_\nu}{\text{Jy}}\right) = 3.07 \times 10^4 \left(\frac{T_e}{\text{K}}\right) \left(\frac{\nu}{\text{GHz}}\right)^2 (1 - e^{-\tau_\nu}) \left(\frac{\Omega}{\text{sr}}\right)$$

$$\tau_\nu = 8.235 \times 10^{-2} \left(\frac{T_e}{\text{K}}\right)^{-1.35} \left(\frac{\nu}{\text{GHz}}\right)^{-2.1} \left(\frac{EM}{\text{pc cm}^{-6}}\right)$$

$$\left(\frac{EM}{\text{pc cm}^{-6}}\right) = \int_0^{s/\text{pc}} \left(\frac{n_e}{\text{cm}^{-3}}\right)^2 d\left(\frac{s}{\text{pc}}\right)$$

- Detect Synchrotron emission

Giant Metrewave Radio Telescope (GMRT)

- 30, 45 m dishes
- 610 MHz (50 cm)
 - Resolution $\sim 5''$
 - FoV $\sim 43'$
- 325 MHz (90 cm)
 - Resolution $\sim 9''$
 - FoV $\sim 81'$
- Target sample: L1551 IRS 5, T Tau & DG Tau
- Epoch: December 2012

T Tau field w GMRT

T Tau with GMRT

T Tau with GMRT

T Tau Spectral Energy Distribution

- GMRT data combined with data from the literature
- SED traces disk at high frequencies and jet at low frequencies
 - Fitted with 2 power-laws using a joint likelihood MCMC method

$$\left(\frac{S_\nu}{\text{mJy}}\right) = K_{323 \text{ MHz}} \left(\frac{\nu}{323 \text{ MHz}}\right)^\alpha + K_{100 \text{ GHz}} \left(\frac{\nu}{100 \text{ GHz}}\right)^{\alpha'}$$

- Measurements at 325 and 610 MHz are consistent with the free-free power-law associated with optically thin/partially optically thick emission extrapolated from cm wavelengths.
- Haven't yet detected spectral turnover.

LOFAR observations

- LOFAR Cycle 1 data:
November 2013 (LC1_001)
- 8 hours of HBA observations
at 150 MHz of T Tau
- 3C147 as flux calibrator
- Averaged to 5s, 4ch per SB
- Reduced data from core &
remote stations on local (DIAS
& ICHEC) resources for initial
study with resolution
comparable to GMRT

LOFAR data reduction strategy

- 250 subbands centred on 149 MHz ~ 2 TB
- Pre-facet calibration (prefactor)
 - Flux calibration (ignoring core-core baselines)
 - Clock – TEC separation
 - Phase calibration with initial GSM
- Phase only direction-independent self-calibration
 - Image 5, 10 SB (2 MHz) chunks at regular intervals
 - Build multi-frequency model of the sky
 - Apply direction independent phase calibration
- SAGECal source subtraction
 - Bright sources subtracted using SAGECal (robust mode)
- Wide-band, wide-field imaging in CASA
- http://www.astron.nl/lofarscience2016/Documents/Wednesday/LSW_Coughlan.pdf

T Tau field w LOFAR

T Tau field with LOFAR vs GMRT

T Tau with LOFAR

vs

GMRT

T Tau with LOFAR

LOFAR detection is consistent with the extended component of T Tau Sb seen at higher frequencies (with position angle of 47° , Loinard+ 2007)

Partially resolved – seems to agree with 610 MHz GMRT extension (Ainsworth+ 2016a)

T Tau with LOFAR

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T Tau with LOFAR

$$\left(\frac{S_\nu}{\text{mJy}}\right) = 7.2 \times 10^{-4} \left(\frac{T_e}{\text{K}}\right) \left(\frac{\nu}{\text{GHz}}\right)^2 (1 - e^{-\tau_\nu}) \left(\frac{\Omega_s}{\text{arcsec}^2}\right) + K_{100 \text{ GHz}} \left(\frac{\nu}{100 \text{ GHz}}\right)^{\alpha_{\text{dust}}}$$

$$\tau_\nu = 8.235 \times 10^{-2} \left(\frac{T_e}{\text{K}}\right)^{-1.35} \left(\frac{\nu}{\text{GHz}}\right)^\eta \left(\frac{\text{EM}}{\text{pc cm}^{-6}}\right)$$

T Tau with LOFAR

$$EM = (1.67 \pm 0.14) \times 10^5 \text{ pc cm}^{-6}$$

$$T_e = (1.4 \pm 0.3) \times 10^4 \text{ K}$$

$$\eta = -1.83 \pm 0.01 \rightarrow S_\nu \propto \nu^{0.17}$$

$$\tau_\nu = 1 \rightarrow \nu = (157 \pm 27) \text{ MHz}$$

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$$= 7.1 \times 10^{-3} \left(\frac{D}{\text{kpc}} \right) \left(\frac{\theta}{\text{arcsec}} \right) \left(\frac{n_e}{\text{cm}^{-3}} \right)^2$$

$$\theta = 3.''27, D = 148 \text{ pc}$$

$$n_e = (7.2 \pm 2.1) \times 10^3 \text{ cm}^{-3}$$

$$M_{\text{ion}} = \frac{4}{3} \pi r_{\text{gas}}^3 m_{\text{H}} n_e = (1.0 \pm 1.8) \times 10^{-6} M_\odot$$

The need for LOFAR International Baselines

- T Tau is complicated
 - Triple system
 - Multiple outflows
 - Competing emission mechanisms
 - Flaring/variability
- Investigate jet launching mechanism
 - 0.3-0.7 arcsec resolution
-> access scales of ~ 40 -100 au.
 - With this resolution, the jet may be resolved not only along the outflow, but also across
-> measure jet opening angle?

New LOFAR observations of T Tau (LC5_004)

- November 2015
- Averaging time steps : 1.0
- Averaging freq steps : 4.0 (16 ch per SB)
- This time and frequency resolution should allow us to adequately uv-shift to a primary phase calibrator within $\sim 1^\circ$ of the phase centre for phase delay calibration.
- Table 1 lists the potential primary (phase delay) and secondary (phase self-cal) calibrators (nearby, bright, and appear compact at 610 MHz with GMRT; see figure) in the target field that should allow for successful long baseline calibration and imaging.

TABLE 1: Proposed VLBI Calibrators

Calibrators	RA (J2000)	Dec (J2000)	$S_{610 \text{ MHz}}$ (mJy)	Distance from target
Primary (for phase delay)	04 19 51.37	+19 20 41.39	340	0°.5
Secondary (for phase self-cal)	04 21 06.6	+19 37 43.56	20	13'
	04 21 18.0	+19 37 20.64	10	11'
	04 21 27.3	+19 41 23.84	40	12'
	04 22 17.2	+19 38 35.91	10	8'
	04 22 36.1	+19 23 43.82	20	12'

T Tau - LC1_001

vs LC5_004

T Tau - LC1_001

vs LC5_004 VLBI

T Tau - LC1_001

vs LC5_004 VLBI

VLBI results & future work

- Non-detection on LOFAR long baselines (or at all for LC5_004)
 - github.com/colmcoughlan/astro-scripts
- Run the VLBI Observations of T Tau through the final LOFAR long baseline pipeline?
 - Likely need a new observation due to non-detection without long baselines
 - Hope to gain insight into the jet launching mechanism on scales <100 au
 - Investigate sources of non-thermal emission in the jets

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